

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Evaluation of Cooperating Teachers on the Teaching Practices of Pre-Service Teachers: The San Isidro College Phenomenon

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ABSTRACT

The overarching focus of this study is on the evaluation of the cooperating teachers (CTs) on the practice teaching performance of the pre-service teachers (PSTs) at San Isidro College for the past three academic years 2015-2016 to 2017-2018. The study utilized the descriptive-qualitative method of research where the written comments of the Cooperating Teachers focused on Planning and Preparation, Instructional Delivery, Classroom Environment; and Professionalism that served as the basis for the evaluation of the PSTs teaching practices. A total of 101 PSTs served as the participants of the study. Findings revealed that the PSTs strengths for the Academic Year 2015 – 2016 up to AY 2017 – 2018 are in Category II on Instructional Delivery, which includes Teaching Methods and Questioning Skills; and in Category IV on Professionalism, which includes Personal, Professional, Social Relationship and Teacher's Personality. The PSTs' strengths are given by their CTs in a friendly or formal and descriptive or evaluative form. The PSTs' areas to be strengthened are in Category I on Planning and Preparation which include Lesson Planning and Content; and in Category III on Classroom Environment, which includes Classroom Management. The CTs' written feedback is a good source of the PSTs' performance and progress in their Practice Teaching during the six-week school experience. The basic phenomenon showed that the performance of the pre-service teachers in this study manifested how they applied the theories, principles, approaches, methods and techniques that they have acquired from San Isidro College.

Key words: *Cooperating Teachers, Pre-Service Teachers, Teaching Practices*

INTRODUCTION

Student Teaching is part of the experiential learning course of the Teacher Education Program. This provides an actual field experience to the Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) in the real learning environment. San Isidro College has started offering Bachelor of Secondary Education in 1965 and offered Bachelor of Elementary Education in 1991.

The Teacher Education graduates had their student teaching experience for both on- and off-campus. These graduates had their on-campus student teaching at the San Isidro College Grade School and High School Departments, while their off-campus teaching was in the Department of Education Cooperating Schools, Malaybalay City Division.

The PSTs do not have other subjects except on Practice Teaching (FS 7) during the second semester of their fourth year level. They have this Field Study 7 at the Department of Education Cooperating Schools for their Off-Campus Student Teaching for six to eight (6-8) weeks. The CTs evaluated the PSTs then with comments on their strengths and weakness or those that need improvement.

The researcher found these comments from the Cooperating Teachers very rich and informative to explore. The Supervising Teacher of Student Teaching have additional comments from the School Heads when she went to the Field and did the class observation of the PSTs. In the light of the new curricula for Teacher Education starting Academic Year 2018-2019, it is an appropriate time to find out

the performance of the PSTs to do the necessary improvement in the Special Pre-Service Exposure (SPSE) Activities and become more ready for the implementation of the new curricula.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This research is based on one of the Special Pre-Service Exposure (SPSE) Activities in the Teacher Education Program where the theories learned by the Pre-Service Teachers are put into practice during the student teaching.

The data gathered from the CTs’ comments or written feedback are illustrated in the first box. The strengths and areas that need to be strengthened were classified according to the adapted categories from Kutztown University of Pennsylvania Clinical Experience Evaluation Form that consist of Planning and Preparation, Instructional Delivery, Classroom Environment and Professionalism. This is reflected in the 2nd box. The comments and suggestions of the CTs to better hone the PSTs in their teaching practices is shown in the third box. Figure 1 shows conceptual schema of the flow of the study

The framework for teacher education proposes the preparation process of teachers be done in such a way that it reflects the paradigm shift from the content-based to competency-based approach in teaching and learning. Schultz (2005) provides support for the concept of day-to-day problem solving capacity development through practicum learning. The study highlighted the need for teacher preparation to support new teacher inquiry to help teacher candidates use problem solving approaches

when they face the day-to-day challenges in a classroom. A study by Brouwer & Korthagen (2005) confirmed the role of the practicum in the overall development of competent teachers. While both classroom theory and practicum experiences were found to be contributors to a new teacher’s development, the practicum in a school context was more influential than the course components of the teacher education program on the development of teaching competence (Msangta, Mkoma & Yihuan, 2016).

Successful teachers are invariably good planners and thinkers. Planning and preparing lessons are fundamental skills all pre-service teachers must develop and hone, although implementation of this skill in actual teaching can, and usually does, take some time. It is accepted that existing teacher education take the school curriculum and textbooks as requisites and train teachers to adjust to the needs of the existing school system through fastidious planning of lessons in standardized formats and fulfilling the ritual of delivering the required number of lessons and hence operates with rigid lesson plan formats (NCFTE, 2010).

Instructional delivery includes all approaches and strategies that a teacher may take to engage students in the learning process actively. These strategies drive a teacher’s instruction as they work to meet specific learning objectives and ensure that their students are equipped with the tools they need to be successful. Effective instructional delivery meets all learning styles and the developmental needs of all learners. Teachers must be equipped with a

Figure 1. The conceptual schema of the study

well-rounded arsenal of effective instructional strategies to maximize their effectiveness and to increase student learning opportunities (Meador, 2019).

Creating a safe, positive classroom environment is key to effective teaching and learning. A classroom environment is a blend of the social, emotional, and instructional elements of the class. Research shows that many aspects of the classroom environment can affect student motivation and that students who are more motivated, put more effort into learning activities (Ambrose, et al., 2010).

Teacher professionalism refers to how teachers conduct themselves with the highest standards in and out of the classrooms. Professionalism encompasses the attributes and characteristics that will define what a professional teacher should be (e.g. passing the licensure exam, adhering to Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers, etc.). The ideal face of teacher professionalism is where teachers are trusted to teach best. Since they know their students best, it is expected that they know what and how to teach. If teachers are reflective, they will know the appropriate teaching strategies, and will be able to handle challenging situations in their diverse and dynamic classrooms (Demirkasimoglu,2010).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study evaluated the Pre-Service Teachers' strengths and areas for improvement in their teaching practices as observed by their Cooperating Teachers during their Off-Campus Student Teaching at the Department of Education's Cooperating Schools in the Malaybalay City Division.

Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What are the Cooperating Teachers' evaluation and comments on the PSTs practice teaching considering:
 - 1.1 Planning and Preparation;
 - 1.2 Instructional Delivery;
 - 1.3 Classroom Environment; and
 - 1.4 Professionalism?
2. What are the comments of the Cooperating Teachers on the strengths and areas that need to be strengthened by the Pre-Service Teachers in their practice teaching phenomenon?
3. What are the written comments of Cooperating Teachers based on pre-service teachers' teaching

checklist in the four categories in practice teaching?

METHODOLOGY

The School of Education at San Isidro College, Impalambong, Malaybalay City is the research locale of the study. The participants were the Pre-Service Teachers in the School of Education at San Isidro College for three (3) consecutive Academic Years; 2015-2016 to 2017-2018. There were 10 BEED and 16 BSED in 2015-16, 10 BEED and 17 BSED in 2016-17. and 16 BEED and 32 BSED in 2017-18 giving a total of one hundred one (101) students. The Pre-Service Teachers had their Off-Campus Student Teaching at the Department of Education, Malaybalay City Division.

The study used the descriptive-qualitative method of research which involved the gathering of data from the Pre-Service Teachers' Student Teaching Rating Sheets for Off – Campus for three academic years 2015 – 2016, 2016 – 2017 and 2017 – 2018 with the written comments of the Cooperating Teachers in the following areas: Planning and Preparation, Instructional Delivery, Classroom Environment; and Professionalism.

The CTs' comments were classified according to the adapted category from Kutztown University of Pennsylvania Clinical Experience Evaluation Form which categories are: Planning and Preparation, Instructional Delivery, Classroom Environment and Professionalism. The data were further qualified using the Spear Model (Spear, 1997) that explores on the form and substance of the written comments or feedback which are friendly or formal, descriptive or evaluative, making suggestions and charting improvements.

The proponents reclassified the (7) performance indicators into the adapted categories since they found out that some indicators are too specific and limiting, the adapted categories include other areas of evaluation of the PSTs' not covered by the Experiential Learning Courses Handbook (ELCH, 2009). The Pre-Service Teacher's Actual Teaching Checklist in the ELCH have some indicators that can be combined in one category.

The results of the tally were classified using the Spear Model that deals with the form and substance of the written feedback or comments given by the

Cooperating Teachers to the Pre-Service Teachers. With the Spear Model the comments were qualified further as friendly or formal, descriptive or evaluative, advisory or making suggestions and charting improvements

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Cooperating Teachers' Comments and Evaluation of Pre-Service Teachers' Teaching Practices

There are areas/categories that serve as bases in evaluating teaching practices. From the *Experiential Learning Course Handbook* entitled *Pre-Service Teachers' Actual Teaching Checklist*. There are six areas of evaluating the practice teaching, namely: Teacher's Personality, Lesson Planning, Content, Teaching Method, Classroom Management and Questioning Skills. Another checklist used was the *Kutztown University of Pennsylvania Clinical Experience Evaluation Form* with four areas: Planning and Preparation (used for evidence collected before and after the lesson), Classroom Environment (used for evidence collected during the lesson), Instructional Delivery (used for evidence collected during the lesson) and Professionalism (used for evidence collected before and after the lesson). The Spear model was also used in this study to further classify the Cooperating Teachers' comments or

written feedback according to the style of writing they used. This attempts to have insights on the form and substance of the written comments as friendly in tone or mainly formal, mainly descriptive or mainly evaluative, whether suggestions are offered and charting improvements. The terms used to describe the aspect or indicator for which the Cooperating Teachers gave comments are: *Praised, Criticized, Suggestions Offered and Mentioned*.

The Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) Actual Teaching Checklist mentioned from the *Experiential Learning Course Handbook* was subsumed for the study based from the *Kutztown University of Pennsylvania (KUP) Clinical Experience Evaluation Form* with the following areas: Planning and Preparation (consists of Lesson Planning and Content), Instructional Delivery (consists of Teaching Methods and Questioning Skills), Classroom Environment (consists of Classroom Management) and Professionalism (consists of Teacher's Personality, Professionalism and Social Relationships).

Table 1 shows the summary of the retrieved comments from the CTs for three school years. These comments were from the Pre-Service Teachers Teaching Checklist (ELCH, 2009) which were accomplished by the CTs. The indicators in the

Table 1. Frequencies of the Retrieved CTs' Comments related to the four areas/ categories

AY	2015 – 2016			2016 – 2017			2017 – 2018		
	No. of Comments	BEED	BSED	No. of Comments	BEED	BSED	No. of Comments	BEED	BSED
Category I: Planning and Preparation (<i>Lesson Planning, Content</i>)	5	1	4	5	1	4	10	6	4
Category II: Instructional Delivery (<i>Teaching methods, Questioning skills</i>)	12	1	11	18	5	13	33	17	16
Category III: Classroom Environment (<i>Classroom Management</i>)	9	1	8	5	0	5	19	9	10
Category IV: Professionalism (<i>Personal/ Professional/ Social Relationship, Teacher's Personality</i>)	24	2	22	21	9	12	50	21	29
Total	50	5	45	49	16	39	112	53	59

checklist were classified according to the adapted categories from the KUP Clinical Experience Evaluation Form which only have four categories. It can be gleaned from the table that the first highest retrieved comments were in Category IV - on Professionalism. This implies that the CTs observed and noted the personal and professional traits of the PSTs.

The teachers as prime movers and facilitators of the teaching and learning processes in the classroom have varied roles. With these varied roles, they are expected to demonstrate the attributes expected of professional teachers that are both personal and professional attributes (Acero, Javier and Castro, 2015). Second in rank of the most retrieved comments is in Category II – on Instructional Delivery. The CTs highlighted suggestions for PSTs to improve especially in the use of teaching methods that can work well in the class as well as the PSTs’ questioning skills.

Comments of the CTs include:

“The PSTs used the teaching methods that were suited to the capabilities and needs of the learners.”

“The PST needs to consider well the method that match the topic with the class size.”

“The PSTs used the IMs to help in the lesson presentation but need to improve some IMs, especially with the size of text, color and size.”

“The PST needs to prepare questions to ask to the class.”

Teaching methods are well planned procedure in the learning activity toward the achievement of the instructional goal (Salandanan, G. 2012). The PSTs’ Practice Teaching Coordinator had conferences with the School Heads or Principals in the Cooperating Schools.

Some of their comments are the following:

“The PSTs are humble enough to seek advice from their CTs and follow the suggestions.”

“The PSTs demonstrate flexibility in the learning environment.”

“The PSTs respond positively on the areas to improve especially in preparing well to have the grasp of the lesson, good delivery of the content and to be firm in their classroom management yet have the interactive class, engage the students.”

“The PSTs really try to connect their lessons to experiences that the learners can

Table 2. Classification of the Comments according to the adapted category

Years	No. of PSTs		Total Comments	INDICATORS				Other Comments
	BEED	BSED		Strengths		Needs to be Strengthened		
				<i>Friendly/formal</i>	<i>Descriptive/evaluative</i>	<i>Advisory/making suggestions</i>	<i>Charting improvements</i>	
2015 – 2016	10		3	3	0	0	0	
		16	51	3	36	0	4	
2016 – 2017	10		22	6	16	0	0	5 students – w/o comments
		17	39	2	36	1	0	5 students – w/o comments
2017 – 2018	16		52	29	16	3	4	
		32	54	38	5	7	4	

relate, and the learners respond positively in class.”

Table 2 shows that the CTS comments for the three academic years on the Pre-Service Teachers’ Teaching Checklist (ELCH, 2009) were grouped based on the adapted category on the Clinical Experience Final Evaluation Form of KUP. Then they were further classified using the Spear Model that explores the form and substance of the written comments or feedback. The indicators on strength include friendly or formal and descriptive or evaluative while the indicators that need to be strengthened include advisory or making suggestions and charting improvements.

The use of the Spear Model allows the researchers to find out that more of the retrieved CTs’ comments belong to the friendly or formal and descriptive or evaluative. This implies that the PSTs have more of the strengths than those that need improvement.

Some of the CTs’ comments supportive of the PSTs include:

“The PSTs are dependable and with potential in teaching with their appropriate tasks, games, strategies and management in their classes.”

“The PSTs demonstrate grasp of their lesson or content with the appropriate prepared IMs and class tasks.”

“The Principals’ comments during the conferences of the Pre – Service Teachers’ Supervising Teacher supports the CTs comments like:

“The PSTs have shown improvements in their lesson preparation, instructional delivery, class management and rapport with the class, the school authorities and the school environment in general.”

The student teachers who experience the life in the actual learning environment - the cooperating schools, where they were deployed by the Department of Education expect, appreciate and get encouraged with the written comments or feedback by their Cooperating Teachers (CTs) about the PSTs’ planning and preparation, the lessons they teach, their classroom management. The PSTs recognize that the written comments of the CTs will help them improve in their teaching in their development as teachers (Christensen, 1988; Frecknall, 1994).

Table 3 shows the classification of the comments according to the adapted category for AY 2015 – 2016. It presents more retrieved comments than the number of PSTs since the PSTs had their shifting in the grade levels during the Practice Teaching. It can be gleaned from the table that the PSTs were given more comments in the Category IV on Professionalism and Teacher’s Personality.

Some comments of the CTs are the following:

“The PST is already prepared in the profession. She has good command of the

Table 3. Classification of the Comments according to the adapted category for AY 2015 – 2016

Categories	No. of Comments	BEED	BSED
Category I: Planning and Preparation (Lesson Planning, Content)	5	1	4
Category II: Instructional Delivery (Teaching methods, Questioning skills)	12	1	11
Category III: Classroom Environment (Classroom Management)	9	1	8
Category IV: Professionalism (Personal/ Professional/ Social Relationship, Teacher’s Personality)	24	2	22
Total	50	5	45

(<https://www.kutztown.edu/.../Clinical%20Experience/FinalEvaluationForm.- Kutztown Univ. of Pennsylvania>)

language too. She is also independent with positive outlook, teachable and willing to improve."

"PSTs maintained desirable rapport with the students, their CTs, School Heads, and in the schools."

"The PSTs have strong personality."

"The PSTs are dynamic and enthusiastic in the class."

The PSTs have more comments that praised them in Category IV on Professionalism where Teacher's Personality is its subsection. This implies the PSTs demonstrate knowledge of professional growth and ethical behavior, communication ability to cultivate good relations with others in school.

Category II on Instructional Delivery ranks second. These were retrieved comments from CTs on their teaching methods and questioning skills.

Comments from CTs are the following:

"The PSTs follow the suggestions and recommendations of the CTs for the choice of strategies for effective teaching and learning."

"The PST handles the teaching and learning processes in appropriate speed with modulated voice that attracts the learners."

"The PST delivers his lesson well. He lets his students participate in the discussion well, with his good questioning skills."

"The PST uses higher order thinking skills (HOTS) questions."

"The PSTs are innovative in handling diverse learners."

"The PSTs use ICT in the class."

In the CTs' comments on Instructional Delivery, the PSTs are also praised. This implies that the PSTs demonstrate a set of procedures in the delivery of their content and the application of the teaching skills in their teaching. The PSTs try to use what works with

the learners for them to be engaged in class meaningfully. In principle, the teacher applies a wide range of teaching process skills. They innovate and create methods to improve student learning (ELCH, 2009).

Strengths and Areas that Need to be Strengthened of the Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) in Practice Teaching

The Pre-Service Teachers play two roles in the actual teaching: as a student and as a teacher. They are also expected to assume responsibility in managing the class and in providing meaningful learning experience to the learners (*San Isidro College Research Journal*). According to Borlasa, K (2006) teaching is never easy. The Pre-Service Teachers commonly described their experience as difficult, tiring and challenging though fulfilling. Among the experiences expressed were using the English language in presenting and explaining the lesson, managing the entire class, presenting complex ideas, motivating the learners and building rapport with the students. She added that most of them expressed their difficulty in coping with the requirements such as lesson plans, test drafts and others that are given by the Cooperating Teachers.

In the Teaching Competencies of the Student Teachers of San Isidro College, the student teachers have the ability to relate effectively with the people they work with. This implies that the student teachers have the strong interpersonal skill. Borlasa (2006) mentioned that student teachers have adequate competence in terms of the functions and tasks of teachers. Lastly, she found out that student teachers have not fully developed their skills in listening and speaking.

The CTs' comments were found out to be supportive of the PSTs and pointed out areas also that need attention which the SED's Special Pre-Service Exposure (SPSE) Activities must address in the Student Teaching Program especially with the implementation of the new teacher education curriculum in AY 2018-2019.

Table 4. Classification of the Cooperating Teachers' Comments into the PST's strengths and areas that need to be strengthened for AY 2015 – 2016

NO. of PSTs	CT's comments	Total Comments	INDICATORS							
			Strengths				Needs to be Strengthened			
			Friendly / formal	%	Descriptive/ evaluative	%	Advisory/ making suggestions	%	Charting improvements	%
10	BEED	3	3	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	BSED	51	3	5.88	36	70.59	0	0	4	7.84

Table 4 shows higher percentage of the CTs comments in the friendly/ formal and descriptive/ evaluative which point out strengths of the PSTs.

The CTs' comments include:

"The PST is good and has a high possibility of becoming a very competent and effective teacher but the PST needs to work on her self – confidence."

"The PSTs demonstrate willingness to learn from their mentors, their CTs in the field."

"The PST shows she has developed the professionalism in acting upon the CTs suggestions."

On the contrary, the PSTs were offered some suggestions by their CTs on some aspects. CTs comments on these are:

"The PST needs to show in – depth knowledge of the subject matter."

"The PST needs to relate his topic to actual life situations, to keep abreast of new ideas."

The indicators offered suggestions which are aspects that need to be strengthened. A CT's comment on charting improvement is:

"The PST has developed the openness to CT's suggestions."

Table 5 shows that in AY 2016 – 2017, more comments were in Category II on Instructional Delivery particularly in the Teaching Methods and Questioning Skills.

The CTs comments are as follows:

"The PSTs use the teaching methods suited to the capabilities of the learners."

"The PST delivers her lesson confidently and articulately."

"The PST has a good command of the language of instruction."

"The PST prepared the IMs that help in the delivery of the lesson that draws the attention of the learners to participate."

"The PST uses ICT to enhance the lesson."

"The PST uses the strategies that fit the learners."

It can also be gleaned from the table that Category IV is second with the most retrieved comments. The CTs' comments:

"The PST provides the positive atmosphere in class."

"The PST is able to manage the classroom situation."

"The PST has the heart to teach children."

"The PST is a kind - hearted teacher."

"The PST is aware of his responsibilities and he is organized."

Table 5. Classification of the Comments according to the adapted category for AY 2016 – 2017

Categories	No. of Comments	BEED	BSED
Category I: Planning and Preparation (Lesson Planning, Content)	5	1	4
Category II: Instructional Delivery (Teaching Methods, Questioning Skills)	18	5	13
Category III: Classroom Environment (Classroom Management)	5	0	5
Category IV: Professionalism (Personal/ Professional/ Social Relationship, Teacher's Personality)	21	9	12
Total	49	16	39

(<https://www.kutztown.edu/.../Clinical%20Experience/FinalEvaluationForm.-> Kutztown Univ. of Pennsylvania)

In AY 2016 – 2017, the PSTs affirmed their choice of methods and strategies that match the lessons, the facility in the medium of instruction and their prepared IMs. Likewise, the CTs have the positive comments in the PSTs' personal attributes in their teaching personality.

Table 6 shows that in AY 2016 – 2017, there is also a higher percentage in the friendly or formal and descriptive or evaluative written feedback of the CTs to the PSTs.

Some comments here that point out the PSTs' strengths are:

"The PST is aware of his responsibilities. He is organized."

"The PST is a very enthusiastic teacher."

"The PST is able to manage the classroom."

"The PSTs use ICT in the class."

Table 6. Classification of the Cooperating Teachers' Comments into the PST's strengths and areas that need to be strengthened for AY 2016 – 2017

NO. of PSTs	CT's comments	Total Comments	INDICATORS								
			Strengths				Needs to be Strengthened				
			Friendly/ formal	%	Descriptive/ evaluative	%	Advisory/ making suggestions	%	Charting improvements	%	
10	BEED	22	6	27.27	16	72.72	0	0	0	0	5 students w/o comments
17	BSED	39	2	5.13	36	92.31	1	2.56	0	0	5 students w/o comments

“The PST is innovative in handling diverse learners.”

“The PSTs’ improve to have interactive class and maximize students’ participation.”

“The PSTs have good pronunciation and command in the language.”

“The PSTs’ need to improve their time management in handling classes.”

“The PSTs’ choice of teaching methods and strategies suit the learners.”

“The PSTs’ have to sustain the interest of the class.”

On the other hand, advisory comments that need to be strengthened among the PSTs are:

The CTs and School Heads’ comments on the PSTs’ performance implies the PSTs needed but to improve in some aspects.

“The PST needs to improve in the use of strategies that match the subject matter.”

In AY 2016 – 2017, the PSTs’ strengths are on instructional delivery and professionalism except for the need to strengthen the classroom management and lesson planning especially on IMs that help more the delivery of the lessons.

“The PST needs to improve his penmanship and IMs.”

“The PSTs need to establish classroom management to maximize class engagement.”

“The PST needs to improve in the use of Filipino language in particular subject areas.”

Table 7 shows that in the Academic Year 2017 – 2018 more comments of the CTs were really in Category IV on Professionalism followed by the Category II on Instructional Delivery. This implies the CTs were able to point the PSTs performance in their use of knowledge of content, use of instructional goals and questioning skills.

The Pre-Service Teachers’ Supervising Teacher had a conference with the School Heads and the following are the comments of the School Heads that affirms the CTs’ comments:

The CTs were able to observe the PSTs’ ethical behavior, professional conduct and professional relations with others in school. Comments of the CTs include:

“The PSTs’ demonstrate positive response and improve on the areas the CTs provided suggestions especially on classroom management, content delivery and use of strategies.”

“The PSTs are challenged to handle difficult, diverse learners but maintain their

Table 7. Classification of the Comments according to the adapted category for AY 2017 – 2018

Categories	No. of Comments	BEED	BSED
Category I: Planning and Preparation (Lesson Planning, Content)	10	6	4
Category II: Instructional Delivery (Teaching Methods, Questioning Skills)	33	17	16
Category III: Classroom Environment (Classroom Management)	19	9	10
Category IV: Professionalism (Personal/ Professional/ Social Relationship, Teacher’s Personality)	50	21	29
Total	112	53	59

(<https://www.kutztown.edu/.../Clinical%20Experience/FinalEvaluationForm.-> Kutztown Univ. of Pennsylvania)

stature as the Practice Teachers, strategize how to proceed with their lessons.”

“The PSTs are open to remarks, show initiative and demonstrate that they learn from the coaching of the CTs.”

“The PSTs are of great help in the school activities, task oriented.”

“The PST is clear with her class rules, shows efforts in preparing for the class, delivers the lessons that are in the scheduled plans.”

“Some PSTs have the language facility, comfortable with English as medium of instruction but with difficulty in the grade levels using Mother Tongue.”

“The PST used real life experience related to the lesson to inculcate values.”

During the PSTs Supervising Teacher’s conference with the School Heads, the CTs comments were confirmed. The following are some of the School Heads’ comments:

“The PSTs stand above the challenges they face in their practice teaching. They find ways to handle problems and deliver their lessons and find out that their learners learned something.”

“The PSTs have improved in their time management in class, in their prepared questions, in using rubric for some class activities.”

“The PSTs improved in their class management especially with the class size.”

The partnership between the Higher Education Institutions (HEI) and the Department of Education for the deployment of the Pre-Service Teachers in their Off- Campus Practice Teaching provides the wider, realistic venue to hone the teaching skills of the Pre-Service Teachers. The Cooperating Teachers are major providers of feedback or comments on the PSTs’ school experience. The School Heads ensures that the PSTs are assigned to qualified Cooperating Teachers and conduct a conference on the PSTs’ performance in coordination with the PSTs’ Supervising Teacher (ELCH, 2009).

Table 8 shows that the CTs’ comments for the PSTs were more of friendly and formal, which express support to the PSTs’ direction to practice their teaching profession.

Some PSTs were given more than one comment. The CTs’ formal comments include:

“The PST, being a teacher in Grade V, whose subject is English, the PST was able to perform a full – cycle of his teaching duties.”

“The PST has a very systematic way of presenting the lesson. He has shown professionalism, passion and commitment in teaching.”

The CTs’ comments were generally supportive of the students but there were also comments that pointed out aspects to improve in the teaching skills of the PSTs.

On the needs to be strengthened the CTs pointed out some advisories or suggestions on some areas like, submitting the Lesson Plan to be checked and make revisions before using it in the class. They were also advised to use appropriate visual aids and to employ interesting class activities.

Table 8. Classification of the Cooperating Teachers’ Comments into the PSTs strengths and areas that need to be strengthened.

NO. of PSTs	CT’s comments	Total Comments	Indicators							
			Strengths				Needs to be Strengthened			
			Friendly/formal	%	Descriptive/evaluative	%	Advisory/making suggestions	%	Charting improvements	%
16	BEED	52	29	55.77	16	30.77	3	5.77	4	7.69
32	BSED	54	38	70.37	5	9.26	7	12.96	4	7.41

**Written Comments of cooperating teachers based on
ELCH pre-service teachers' teaching checklist***Category I- Planning and Preparation*

Under Category I on Planning and preparation the highlight is on Lesson Planning in the adapted category in the KUP. These include comments on whether the lesson is well prepared. It also checked on the congruence between objectives and subject matter; objectives and teaching procedures; objectives and formative test; and objectives and assignment. The CTs praised the PSTs in the indicator on the lesson as being well-prepared for the AY 2017 – 2018. However, some CTs offered suggestions also in the AY 2015 – 2016 and AY 2017 – 2018 under the preparation of the lesson.

The CTs gave comments like:

"The PST need to improve in his lesson planning, to include strategies to suit the learners' capacity and needed skill."

"The PST needs to improve in preparation and appropriateness of IMs for the class to interact."

The result in the area highlights the important collaboration of the Cooperating Teacher and the Student Teacher to plan together; divide up subjects, each taking primary responsibility for certain content areas; initiate instruction and share ideas; review assessments and reflect together on the effectiveness of the lessons (Cooperating Teacher Roles and Responsibilities, Office of Field Placement Resources, 2017).

Under the Category on Content in the ELCH adapted category from KUP, the indicators include the following: the teacher demonstrates in-depth knowledge of the subject matter; the teacher is able to relate lessons to actual life situations; keeps abreast of new ideas and understanding in the field; and gives sufficient and concrete examples to create meaningful experiences. The PSTs received more praised in the friendly or formal tone in their in-depth knowledge of the subject matter. They keep abreast of the new ideas and understanding in the field for AY 2015 – 2016 to AY 2017 – 2018.

CTs' comments include:

"The PST has good preparation that is important in the process of teaching."

"The PST is active and creative."

"The PST's performance in the class demonstrates meaningful understanding of the subject matter."

"The PST teaches well prepared lesson plan. She shows mastery of the subject matter."

Category II - Instructional Delivery

The indicator on teaching methods include the following: the methods used were suited to the needs and capabilities of the learners; the teacher was creative enough to adapt his/her teaching method to the student's capabilities; visual aids and other examples were used to illustrate the lesson; the teacher made effective use of the formative test after teaching.

In AY 2015 – 2016 to AY 2017 – 2018, the CTs praised the PSTs in their use of teaching methods that were suited to the needs and capabilities of the students and in their creative methods that were suited also to the students' capabilities. Some comments of the CTs include the following:

"The PSTs are innovative in handling the diverse learners."

"The PSTs use or integrate technology in the instruction and maintain an interactive class."

"The PST has the ability to teach, following the different steps of the plan with corresponding varied teaching materials to match the students' needs and abilities."

These imply that the PSTs demonstrate a set of procedures in the delivery of their content and the application of the teaching skills in their teaching areas. The PSTs try to use what works with the learners for them to participate and be engaged in class meaningfully. The teacher applies a wide range of teaching process skills and creates and innovates alternative teaching methodologies to improve student learning (Experiential Learning Courses Handbook, 2009).

The questioning skills of the teacher stimulates discussion in different ways such as: probing for learner's understanding; helping student's articulate their ideas and thinking process; promoting risk-taking and problem solving; facilitating factual recall; encouraging convergent and divergent thinking; stimulating curiosity; and helping students to ask questions. The CTs commented on the PSTs' questioning skills. The CTs praised the PSTs that they can ask questions that encourage divergent and convergent thinking that stimulates curiosity.

Category III- Classroom Environment (Classroom Management)

Under this category the teacher has a systematic way of checking: attendance; assignment, homework, agreement; practice exercises and drills; group work and projects; passing in and out of the room; correcting, distributing and collecting papers. This category also checks on the order and discipline in the classroom; moreover, it checks if the visual aids are within the easy reach of the teacher during the act of teaching. Among the indicators in the classroom management, the PSTs received more "praises" on the indicator order and discipline which were evident in the classroom during the AY 2017 – 2018.

However, suggestions were also offered in the AY 2017 – 2018 on order and discipline in class which also play an important role to ensure that learning takes place. The comments of the CTs include:

"The PST's performance on classroom management is evident."

"The PST has the command in the class."

"I like the PST's students' discipline."

"He knows how to discipline his learners."

"She imposes good discipline by making a strategic group point system."

On the other hand, there were comments that need to be strengthened like:

"The PST needs to improve her classroom management, to check the attendance is very important."

"The PST has to improve her classroom management in handling the pupils."

"The PST is reminded that imposing discipline in class is really needed and should monitor the learners always"

Category IV- Professionalism (Personal/ Professional/ Social Relationship, Teacher's Personality)

Under Teacher's personality, the following are evaluated: the teacher is neat and clean; the teacher is free from mannerisms that tend to disturb the students' attention; the teacher's personality is strong enough to command respect and attention; the teacher shows dynamism and enthusiasm. In the AY 2015 – 2016, the PSTs received praises in their dynamism and enthusiasm in class and in their strong personality to command respect and attention in class. These comments were written in the friendly or formal style:

"The PSTs have strong personality. Good in classroom management."

"The PSTs are dynamic and enthusiastic in class."

In the year 2016 – 2017, the CTs also highlighted these performance indicators of the PSTs. This implies that the PSTs demonstrate their personal traits that the future teachers are expected to have. Classroom management sets the tone of the Classroom environment that allows learning and engagement of the learners.

Under personal/professional/social relationships the following are evaluated: The PSTs enjoy rapport with the CTs and fellow teachers; Is generally cheerful and displays wholesome sense of humor; Listens to, considers and acts upon suggestions of the cooperating teachers; Cooperates in all activities; Reports to class regularly to teach and is punctual; Accomplishes requirements of cooperating teacher and passes it on time; Imposes discipline in a firm but kind and humane manner; Send notice and arrangement on time to CT when absent; and Comes to class prepared.

In the AY 2017 – 2018, the CTs praised the PSTs more in their cheerful disposition and display of wholesome sense of humor. The PSTs were praised for their responsive consideration and acting upon on the suggestions of the CTs.

Suggestions were also offered by the CTs for the PSTs to accomplish requirements in the Student Teaching and to pass them on time. Comments of the CTs' include:

"The PST needs to manage her time."

"I suggest that lesson plan will be submitted before holding the class."

"Ipasa ang LP bago magsimula ang linggo o bagong paksa."

"Kailangan lamang na kung ano man ang hinihingi ay maipasa ito sa takdang oras na pinag-usapan."

CONCLUSIONS

Practice teaching is an important component towards becoming a teacher. It provides experiences to student teachers in the actual teaching and learning environment. During teaching practice, a student-teacher is given the opportunity to try the art of teaching before actually getting into the real world of the teaching profession. The feedback and comments of Cooperating teachers could help hone the skills of the Pre-service teachers.

In this study the PSTs strengths in their teaching practices for the Academic Year 2015 – 2016 up to AY 2017 – 2018 are in Category II Instructional Delivery (Teaching Methods and Questioning Skills); and in Category IV Professionalism (Personal, Professional, Social Relationship and Teacher's Personality). The PSTs strengths are given by their CTs in a friendly or formal and descriptive or evaluative form.

The PSTs' areas to be strengthened for the Academic Years 2015 – 2016 up to Academic Years 2017 – 2018 are in Category I – Planning and Preparation (Lesson Planning and Content); and in Category III – Classroom Environment (Classroom Management). The CTs' comments or written feedback can be a good source of the PSTs'

performance and progress in their Practice Teaching during the six – week school experience. The friendlier or formal feedback of the CTs to their PSTs are supportive of the students. The descriptive or evaluative feedback not only record features that deserved praise but also pointed out aspects that required further attention. The CTs' written feedback or comments especially in the areas that need to be strengthened: Category I – Planning and Preparation (Lesson Planning and Content); Category III – Classroom Environment (Classroom Management) provided suggestions or advisory. CTs offered helpful suggestions. They were charting improvements on following the PSTs' progress in some specific areas namely in their lesson planning and preparation, in the lessons or content they teach and in their classroom management.

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